

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT ON 3D SANDWICH: EFFECT OF THE STITCHING STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS

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SUMMARY: This paper deals with the stitched sandwich behaviour under impact and the residual post-impact performances. A particular attention is given to the influence of the stitching parameters (angle and step of stitching). Under low velocity impact and during compression after impact tests, the specific behaviours to these structures are studied with techniques of investigation like the acoustic emission. The failure modes are also studied in direct relation with the stitching parameters. This study clearly shows the potentials as of the this type of structure compared to a unstitched conventional solutions.

KEYWORDS: mechanical testing, low velocity impact, CAI, sandwich, stitching, acoustic emission

INTRODUCTION

Typically, a sandwich is a particular type of laminated composite characterized by different parts associated together to cooperate with their own properties giving to the whole structure its global performance. The face sheets are bonded to the core, and carry most of the bending and in-plane loads. The core provides the flexural stiffness and out-of-plane shear and compressive strength. The structural performance of sandwich panels depends not only on the properties of the skins, but also on those of the core, the adhesive bonding the core to the skins, and the geometrical dimensions of the components.

The primary weakness of sandwiches is generally their low strength in the through thickness direction controlled by the core behaviour, making inter-laminar delamination a major concern in their structural. A new technology of through-the-thickness reinforcement already in use in case of monolithic [1-3] is transposed in case of sandwich structures: adding fiber reinforcement in the third direction to improve cohesion and inter-laminar strength. For the sandwich structures, mechanical improvement due to stitches has already been shown [4, 5] and the influence of the structural parameters such as density and angle of stitching has been also studied.

The aim of this study is to conduct an investigation concerning the effect of stitching under low velocity impact test. Moreover, effect of such an impact on residual strength will be evaluated with compression after impact test. A particular attention will be given to the mode of failure involved by the stitch's presence.

MATERIAL PRESENTATION

A sandwich structure consists of lightweight core material bonded to two thin face sheets of stronger and stiffer material. The stitched sandwich is produced from a traditional sandwich panel by introducing rows of stitches whose role is to reinforce the link between the two face sheets and eventually increases the mechanical properties in the third direction (fig. 1).

In this paper, the material is constituted of two skins made from 2 plies of woven plain glass (440 g/m²), a 35 kg/m³ polyurethane foam core and the stitches composed of two 2400 Tex glass yarns.

Fig. 1: A stitched sandwich : schematization and photograph (foam removed)

The total thickness of the panels, after injection of polyester resin (RTM process) is 22 mm : 20 mm core thickness and each skin has a thickness of 1 mm.

Due to the stitching process, the spacing between the rows is 25 mm and cannot be changed. The studied parameters are the angle and the step of stitches. Table 1 shows the different panels used in this work. The stitched panel with 45° angle and 25 mm step will be used as a reference. The other panels differ from this one by only one parameter (angle or stitch density). It is also important to introduce the unstitched sandwich in order to evaluate the contribution of the stitches on mechanical behavior.

Table 1: Configurations of materials

	Stitches	
	angle	Step
unstitched	None	
stitched ref.	45°	25 mm
stitched 60°	60°	25 mm
stitched 50 mm	45°	50 mm
stitched 12,5 mm	45°	12,5 mm

Weight is an important attribute of the sandwich structure. However, introducing stitches increases the weight of the panel as shown in table 2. The 50 mm step stitch rows increase the weight by only 10% whereas the 12,5 mm step stitches increase the weight by 50%. Such weight increase should have an important influence on the specific properties.

Table 2: Areal weight of the panels

	unstitched	stitched ref.	stitched 60°	stitched 50 mm	stitched 12,5 mm
Weight (kg/m ²)	5.45	6.36	6.12	6.04	8.18

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT BEHAVIOUR

Experimental procedure

Drop-weight impact testing was performed to investigate the effects of stitching on damage resistance of sandwich panels.

The dimensions (310mm x 150mm) of the specimen were chosen to allow compression after impact testing to be performed.

Fig. 2: impactor device

Impact testing was performed using an instrumented drop weight impact system of the laboratory as schematized by figure 2. The impact tester consisted of a 35 kN capacity load cell and a 20 000g accelerometer mounted onto a crossbeam. The crossbeam was attached to two vertical guide columns with linear bearings. The indenter head was threaded into the load cell and the crossbeam was raised to the height that produced the desired input energy for impact testing. The weight of the indenter head, load cell, and crossbeam was 13 kg. The impact force produced during the impact event was recorded as a function of time using a PC-based data acquisition system.

Prior to impacting, specimens were centred and clamped on both ends onto the base plate of the impactor which contained a 100mm diameter hole centred directly beneath the impact head. Impacting was performed using a 50mm diameter hemispherical impactor and impact energies were 130J.

Impact force was recorded as a function of time during each impact event.

Results and effect of the structural parameters

Effect of stitching on transmission of the deformation from one skin to another.

Fig. 3 : strain gages during impact test

During the impact, strain gages are stuck on the two faces of the sample as shown in figure 3. One is located on the upper face which directly receives the impact and the other on the lower face. Information collected allow to judge of the strain transmission the from one skin to another and to determine if the presence of the stitches preserves the unimpacted face.

Figure 4 presents these strain (μdef) by comparing an unstitched structure and its equivalent stitched during the first moments of the impact.

Fig. 4: comparison of deformation of the two skins under impact (a): unstitched (b) stitched ref.

The unstitched structure (figure 4a) presents a significant strain of the upper face followed by a strain of the same amplitude of the un-impacted face. The delay between the beginning of the two strains corresponds to the compression of foam. This one transmits the efforts in a not deadened way as soon as its maximum of compression is reached.

Concerning the stitched structure, the upper skin's strain is comparable with that recorded for the unstitched one (same strain speed and same amplitude). On the other hand, the lower skin only undergoes very little the effects of the impact: Its strain is very low throughout the impact.

Fig. 5: impact zone of the stitched specimen (foam removed)

The 3d structure created by the stitches is degraded during the impact as shown by figure 5. The energy delivered during the impact is absorbed by the degradation of the upper skin and the stitches. The lower skin does not undergo degradation. Foam plays a relatively small role of absorption compared to the stitches.

Effect of the stitching angle.

During impact, the indenter head exerts a transverse compression localised on the stitches. The buckling of these stitches is most of the time responsible of the failure. As the stitching angle is defined from the horizontal, a 60° stitch will be more vertical than a 45° stitch and will be thus more sensitive to buckling. Figure 6 compares the evolution of the load measured for a 45° stitched sandwich and a 60° stitched sandwich.

Fig. 6: typical evolution of load during impact comparing the influence of stitching angle

In any cases, the stitched material's performances are higher than the unstitched sandwich structure one which presents an irregular evolution of load characterized by foam/core delamination.

In both cases of stitched materials, load grows in an identical way in a first part. The 60° stitched specimen presents a better linearity than the 45° stitched specimen. Nevertheless the failure of the 45° stitched specimen is carried out brutally by simultaneous failure of the requested stitches. Concerning the 60° stitched specimen, the failure is carried out by stages which correspond to the successive failure of the stitches by buckling. These failures are shown by the figure 6b where the point of anchoring is the weak point of the structure.

Fig. 7: 60° stitched sandwich under impact : (a) deformation of the skins and (b) degradation of the stitches

Concerning the strain transmission, figure 7a gives the evolution of the strain recorded by the two gages. The upper skin strain is almost the same than the 45° stitched specimen one. But concerning the lower skin, in a first time, strain is limited and becomes higher when stitches break one by one. After complete ruin of the 3D structure, strain is transmitted to the lower skin in the same manner as the unstitched sandwich.

Effect of the stitching step.

The stitching step determines the quantity of reinforcement in the third direction and controls the rigidity of the whole structure [4]. The reference material presents a 25mm stitching step. Two other natures of reinforcement were evaluated : a 12.5mm and a 50mm step. These three structures were subjected to a impact and figure 8 shows the evolution of the load during this 130J impact.

Fig. 8: typical evolution of load during impact comparing the influence of stitching step

Decreasing the stitching step increases the whole structure rigidity and also allows a higher maximum loading. The failure, characterized by a brutal load fall, is quite as brutal for a step of 12.5 mm as for 25 mm. The value obtained after failure is the same one. Then, increasing the step while passing from 25 mm to 50 mm, preserves a rigidity equivalent. Moreover, the return to the value post-rupture is done a little less quickly. This behaviour is halfway between the reference stitched structure and the unstitched one. Indeed, more the stitching step will be high, more the behaviour will tend towards the unstitched one. This is confirmed by the strain transmission presented by figure 9. Initially, the structure resists and the un-impacted face does not undergo significant strain. Nevertheless beyond a certain value of effort, the stitches break (figure 8b) and a unstitched structure is found : the strain is transmitted from the impacted skin towards the un-impacted one.

Fig. 9: 50 mm stitched sandwich under impact : (a) deformation of the skins and (b) degradation of the stitches

POST-IMPACT BEHAVIOUR : RESIDUAL STRENGTH

Experimental procedure

The objective of the edgewise compression testing was to determine whether stitching and medium skin improve the in-plane load carrying capacity of sandwich structures and to quantify the improvements in ultimate failure. As a mean of testing residual strength, compression was also chosen because it is among the most critical loading conditions for composites materials.

Edgewise compression testing was carried out according to ASTM C364.

Fig. 10: CAI device

End loading fixtures were machined to clamp and hold the top and bottom edges of the specimens. These fixtures were designed to prevent localized damage at the ends of the face sheets. Anti-buckling devices maintained the two unloaded edge.

Edgewise compression specimens were cut to a length of 310mm. This length allowed for a 15mm unsupported gage length when the specimens were clamped in the test fixture. Specimens were 150mm wide.

The specimens were loaded at a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min until significant load drop was observed in the load-displacement curve, which was attributed to the final failure or buckling.

Results and effect of the structural parameters

The failure mode during this test is deeply modified by the presence of the stitches. Indeed, an unstitched structure will undergo a global buckling (figure 11a) whereas the presence of the stitches involves a ruin of material by brutal failure of the skins by shearing (figure 11b). This failure occurs by starting from a point of weakness of the structure: after an impact, it is the zone of impact which is used as starter.

Fig. 11: mode of failure (a) unstitched material (b) stitched material

To apprehend this behaviours, the acoustic emission technology is used to apprehend the type of degradations during the CAI tests and their evolution. Figure 12 shows the evolution of the number of events classified by amplitude in dB during the time of the test.

Fig. 12: acoustic emission signature of non impacted specimen during Compression After Impact testing : (a) unstitched (b) stitched

Concerning the not impacted unstitched sandwich, figure 12a shows very few events located in a zone ranging between 35dB and 65dB, relating to ruptures within the resin and of the interface fibre/resin [5]. The events concerning the fibre ruptures ranging between 75dB and 100dB are limited enough. The failure of such a unstitched structure is carried out primarily by buckling.

As regards the stitched sandwich, figure 12b shows a completely different behaviour. Beyond those centred around 50 db (matrix degradation), the failure produce much more events at high amplitude synonymous of stitch failure.

The performances of material depend on its capacity to be opposed to buckling. Consequently, the presence of the stitches ensures this maintains. Stitching parameters such as step and angle have been tested and influence on rigidity and maximum load has been determined.

Effect of the stitching parameters on post-impact rigidity.

Figure 13 presents a comparison of the rigidities (N/mm) determined during CAI tests. The influence of the step and the angle stitching is highlighted before and after impact.

First, before impact, the presence of the stitches increases the rigidity by 15% compared to the unstitched structure. Moreover, the stitching parameters do not have any influence: whatever the angle or the step, rigidity is the same.

On the other hand, after impact, stitching step has the most influence. A small step limits degradations to an area restricted around the point of impact. Thus, the 12.5mm stitched structure is not really disturbed by the impact in term of rigidity. Moreover, more the step is large, more the behaviour tends towards that of the unstitched sandwich. It is interesting to notice that the loss of rigidity is directly related to the step. The stitching angle does not have an influence on the post-impact behaviour.

Fig. 13: effect of the structural parameter of stitching on rigidity under CAI test

Effect of the stitching parameters on post-impact maximum load.

Figure 14 presents the results of the CAI test in term of maximum loading. It informs about the propagation and the seriousness of degradations. Indeed, the total ruin of material will appear when degradations are propagated in the whole structure.

Before impact, the overall increase in rigidity involved by the presence of the stitches allows the stitched structures to better resist. Thus, a weak stitching step will involve a higher maximum loading. This value is 4.5 times higher for the 12.5 mm stitched sandwich than for unstitched one. The value increase is directly connected with the reduction in the stitching step in a significant way. A high angle (vertical) seems to cause harmful stress concentrations for ultimate resistance. Thus, the 45° angle reaches a value 30% higher than that the one reached by a 60° stitched structure.

After impact, the losses are in the same orders of magnitude (approximately 40-50%) whatever the step stitching. Regarding to the stitching angle, the maximum loading is the same one for the two values of angle: the quantity of damaged stitches is identical (same density) and the propagation of degradations occurs early in both cases.

Fig. 14: effect of the structural parameter of stitching on maximum load under CAI test

CONCLUSION

The increase in the performances generated by the implementation of reinforcements in the thickness direction is clearly highlighted in this study. The capacities for absorption and resistance under an impact gives to this type of material a high structural potential. Moreover, the study of the stitching parameters (step and angle) put obviousness the need for adapting the structure to the desired behaviour. The possibilities offered by these stitched structures give the opportunity to design rigid and resistant materials as well that “fusible” materials able to absorb the impact energy. The post-impact performances are also definitely improved. It is possible to conceive a structure in which the stitching density will be just sufficient to ensure of good performances post-impact without increasing the mass beyond the necessary. The concept of optimization is one of the points strong of these composite structures.

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